

IMPLEMENTATION OF SCIENTIFIC-RESEARCH WORKS FOR THE PURPOSE OF A NEW APPROACH IN THE TEACHING OF SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS

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Abstract: this article talks about the process of teaching specialized subjects and the importance of using educational and methodological support in it, and improving the educational and methodological support on this basis.

Key words: specialty subject, educational and methodological support, teaching, educational process.

Introduction:

On September 23, 2020, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Law "On Education" in a new version, and on the basis of this law, educational reforms were further improved. The development strategy of New Uzbekistan was determined today by the adoption of the Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026. is one of the most important reforms of the day.

Scientific research is the process of studying, experimenting, experimenting, conducting expertise and verifying the theory related to the reception of scientific knowledge.

Interdisciplinary research requires the participation of experts in different fields and is carried out in several scientific associations. A comprehensive study is carried out using methods and approaches that scientists seek to cover the highest possible number of important parameters of the studied reality.

Critical studies are conducted to determine which of the existing theories, models, hypotheses, laws, etc. are more accurate. Critical research has a rich and empirical supply of knowledge, and there are empirical methods that have been collected and tested to carry out the experiment.

Any research results must be replicated in a similar experiment conducted by another scientist with the appropriate authority. Therefore, after discovering new effects and patterns, it becomes possible to create new techniques. The operations performed during training should be repeated by any qualified researcher.

Modern scientific-theoretical thinking strives to get into the essence of the studied phenomena and processes. This is possible under the condition of a holistic approach to the object under study, taking into account the object in its emergence and development, i.e. using a historical approach.

In the scientific sense, learning means looking into the future. Imagination, fantasy, dream based on the real achievements of science and technology - these are the most important factors of scientific research.

To learn scientifically is to be scientifically objective. Facts cannot be rejected because they are difficult to explain or because they are difficult to find practical use for. The fact is

that the essence of innovation in science is not always visible to the researcher. New scientific facts and even discoveries may remain in the reserve of science for a long time and not be used in practice, because their meaning is not well understood.

Developing an idea to the problem-solving stage is usually done as a planned process of scientific research. Science also knows accidental discoveries, but only planned, well-equipped scientific research with modern tools can reliably reveal and deeply understand objective laws in nature. In the future, the process of targeted and general conceptual processing of the initial concept will be continued, clarifications, changes, additions will be made, and the intended research scheme will be developed.

Scientific research is objective knowledge, the results of which are manifested in the form of a system of concepts, laws and theories.

The purpose of conducting scientific research on the problems of teaching special subjects is to learn how to solve problems related to teaching and learning, the development and practical application of effective methods, and the use of information and technical tools. In order to conduct scientific research, a teacher must have a deep knowledge of the content of the subject. Many future pedagogues are engaged in pedagogical research during their student days. They prepare methodical instructions, models, and materials for independent work. They improve their pedagogical skills by participating in scientific conferences and seminars with their lectures..

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